

COMPOSITION AND OCCUPATIONS OF RESIDENTS OF THE CITY OF MARGILAN

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Abstract. According to the conclusions of many researchers who studied the issues of cities in the civilization of Central Asia and Uzbekistan, which is a part of it, this process had an urbanistic character from its beginning to the next stages of development. The urbanization processes of the period we are studying in the Fergana Valley are no exception. This article is about the city of Margilan.

Key words. Turkish-speaking and Persian-speaking population, "seed", "elat", "class", "tribe", tailoring, cotton, silk.

The city of Margilan has a complex ethnic composition, the main part of the population is made up of Uzbeks who lived in different parts of it. Researchers show that their composition consists of three major sub-ethnic groups. The first of them was formed by the settled population who lived in cities and villages since ancient times, and this group did not have a clan-tribal system. The nomadic and semi-nomadic population called them "sart". It is known that this group was formed as a result of the assimilation of the ancient Turkic-speaking and Persian-speaking people who lived between two rivers in Central Asia.

The second sub-ethnic group is the Turks, who are made up of Turkish and Turko-Mongol clans and settled in Central Asia before the campaigns of Muhammad Shaibani Khan. These are Yagmo, Qarluq, Chigil, Ashpar, Turukshar, Chogrok, Kavchin, Jaloyir, Barlos, Naiman, Khitay, Min, Kirq, Churas, Kangli, Bahrin, Norin, Togay, Duglot, Otarchi, Argin and others. These words of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur about the people of Andijan clearly describe this category of people: "Eli is a Turk. There is no one who does not know Turkish in the city and market. Eli's words are painful and arousing."

The third sub-ethnic group of the Uzbek population is the descendants of Dashti Kipchak clans who came to Movarounnahr at the end of the 15th century and the beginning of the 16th century with Muhammad Shaibani Khan. They included bells, qiyats, qatagons, kenagas, mangits, palaces, faces, kipchaks, three-seeds, and others. They mainly lived in Margilan, Andijan, Aravon, Osh and Uzgan. Also, the clans belonging to this group took possession of the lands

between Namangan, Chortoq and Navkat in the late 17th - early 18th centuries and began to settle there."

The works written by local historians play an important role in the study of the ethnic composition of the Uzbeks and other ethnic groups, which formed the basis of the population of Margilan, and in making an impartial assessment of it. The historical works written by local historians contain some valuable information about the ethnic composition of the city's population and the location of ethnic groups, in which the population is recorded with expressions such as "community", "seed", "elite", "category", "tribe".

In the composition of the population, the settled population is the majority compared to the nomadic and semi-nomadic population. According to economic activities, the majority of the settled population was engaged in agriculture, handicrafts and trade, while the nomadic and semi-nomadic population was engaged in animal husbandry.

Handicrafts and handicrafts played an important role in the daily activities of Margilon residents. With a long history of development, the craft of Margilon was highly specialized. In handicrafts, there were even branches focused on the production of one type of goods and one part of them. This can be observed especially in weaving and blacksmithing. Artisans are skilled craftsmen who have mastered the secrets of their profession perfectly, and are able to raise their products to the level of high art.

Craftsmen tried to ensure the high quality of their products. And fierce competition in the market encouraged them to keep the secrets of their professions secret. The finer points of trades were taught only to children, sometimes to apprentices, and in this way it was passed down from generation to generation.

The main part of the population of Margilon was engaged in handicrafts and handicrafts. Neighborhoods had special workshops, teams and shops depending on their specialized craft. This can be seen from the names of neighborhoods and streets in the city.

Although the development of crafts was the same in almost all neighborhoods of Margilon, the production was distinguished by some of its features, that is, the type and quality of the product. Blacksmithing, jewelry, weaving, carpentry, pottery, coppersmithing and other branches of handicrafts³ are widely developed, and they spread the grain with the products they produced in a particular field. According to the information provided by A.P.

Khoroshkhin about Margilan crafts, the production of atlas, silk, adras, and bekasam fabrics is an area worthy of attention.

Masters produced high-quality products in Margilon. There are many experienced craftsmen in Kok, who, raising their products to the level of art, have regular customers and clients. This indicates that the craftsmen are provided with permanent work.

Production in the city of Margilon is based on manual labor, and the main crafts are weaving thread and silk fabrics, making shoes, leather processing, making pottery, blacksmithing, making saddles and harnesses, painting, coppersmithing, jewelry, carpentry, carriage making, military weapons production. drawing, carving, wax making, pistachio coal making, embroidery, hat making, covering thick roofs and so on.

In Russian sources, it is noted that women were the main productive force in handicrafts. They "spun cotton and silk, wove elegant and high-quality fabrics from them, sewed shirts and other clothes for themselves and their customers. And men mainly did pottery, tanning (leather processing) and heavy work."

In the city, the main property was in the hands of the ruling classes, and small merchants and artisans paid a certain amount for the use of this land.

Margilan handicrafts are rich and rich in content, and according to their social status, craftsmen are divided into two classes: upper and lower classes. The representatives of the upper class included craftsmen who had their own workshops, tools and raw materials. The lower class was made up of those who used the workshops and tools of labor in the hands of the propertied classes, and those who worked as laborers and porters in the hands of the masters belonging to the upper class.

In Margilon, the townspeople were engaged in many professions. Each craftsman lived in his own village, worked in special workshops, stalls, shops and made a living. In many neighborhoods of Margilon, there were neighborhoods of coppersmiths, blacksmiths, potters, locksmiths, locksmiths, degrez (boiler pourers), cloth weavers, archers and other craftsmen. Artisans and artisans were engaged in the work inherited from ancient times and became skilled and masters in their professions. Many cities and districts of Margilon specialized in some craft and were famous for their products. As mentioned above, residents of Margilon were famous for the production of silk gauze (atlas, alacha, bekasam).

Jewelers used to buy raw materials for their products from the markets of Margilon. Jewelry products were sold at a low price, and they were mainly

delivered by merchants to Russian markets and fairs, and thus cheaply these goods filled the coffers of the rich Europeans. Jewelers skillfully made all kinds of gold rings, necklaces with gold structure, gold-eyebrows, rings, wrist rings, bracelets, amulets, and decorated swords, knife handles, sheaths with precious stones. Turquoise, ruby, ruby, emerald, red-ruby, and blue agates, which are important raw materials for jewelry, were found around Khojand, in Sokh and Isfara mountains, in Oloy. They were sold in the markets of Kokan, Margilon and Tashkent. In the 19th century, a pound of lojuvard was sold for 25 to 40 gold.

Among the artisans of the Fergana governorate, craftsmen and artisans who made weapons and war clothes had a great reputation and respect. Cannon makers, gunsmiths, gunsmiths, gunsmiths, hoe makers, spearsmiths, armorers, hatters lived in Kokon, Oratepa and Margilon. During the time of Khudoyor Khan, there was a special enterprise in Kok that produced gunpowder. Gunpowder was produced in Margilon. A European-style rifle factory was built in Andijan, where rifles and other weapons were repaired.

In the 2nd half of the 19th century, craftsmen and artisans working with tailoring, cotton and silk fell into a difficult situation. The first reason for this is the conflicts of governors - internal conflicts, and secondly, cotton and silk are sold in Russian markets and they are re-produced in Russian factories, and these products are brought back to Margilon and sold to the population at low prices. As a result, the weavers' market will suffer and their condition will worsen. Many of these professions gradually disappeared. Obzhuvoz - paper mills operated in Margilon. The products of the paper industry were usefully used by scribes, calligraphers, book-coverers, artists, painters and draftsmen. The population of Margilan was formed by the Turkic peoples, and they led a sedentary life. Uzbeks and Tajiks living in the city were engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry, crafts and trade.

As the main wealth of Margilon was land, fertile lands were considered state property. At the end of the 19th century, one of the specialized branches of the economy was handicrafts, which included weaving, pottery, blacksmithing, coppersmithing, carpentry and other types. Most of the products produced by them were sold in domestic markets, and some were sold in fairs and markets of neighboring countries and Russia. At the end of the 19th century, industrial products produced in Russia increased rapidly in the markets. These cheap products gave a big blow to the local artisans and started to harm many artisans.

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